

Control Design of a UAV using Deep Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract

The goal of this research is to design In-flight control systems of UAVs using deep reinforcement learning. Although traditional control systems have shown state-of-the-art results, they are often locked to a certain system and are static making it a very time-consuming process to design control systems.

To design an accurate model, the study first discusses the underlying hardware, sensors, airframe and aerodynamics of the UAV. The process of mapping the physical system to a mathematical model is then described.

PWM level hardware access is not provided in most UAVs and thus the Parrot Minidrone series was chosen with Matlab as the development/simulation tool to perform experiments and view results.

Once the model was ready, it was deployed to a real-world drone to validate its dynamics and to prove that the simulations were accurate. In this case, traditional controllers like PID were used and their limitations were shown which formed the basis for shifting to generic methods like Deep Reinforcement Learning.

There are several Reinforcement Learning techniques but DDPG was chosen as the preferred method due to its ability to handle continuous action spaces.

Finally, this study deep dives into the various training methods/parameters used for training the RL agent and how a stable flight was achieved to create a dynamic model which would not only work for the current system i.e. a Quadcopter, but can be applied to any UAV with minor changes in observations and action values.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) like Quad/Tri copters and fixed winged aircrafts are very popular these days with a wide range of applications such as Reconnaissance, Archaeology, Filming and Military Operations.

Recent trends show that drones will be at the forefront of automation in near future and with services like Amazon Prime making them the preferred method delivery shows their potential and the challenges faced in their deployment.

Traditionally, designing control systems of UAVs has been a very painstaking task and requires extensive mathematical modeling. Models, which are often linearized and don't accurately map the real-world aerodynamics of the air frame and thus lead to overshoots in controllers like the infamous PID controller.

In Addition, the slightest of changes in controllable and non-controllable variables like weight, gravity, wind, ground effects and damage to airframe may render the controller ineffective.

Artificial Intelligence has been at the forefront of self-driving cars and autonomous vehicles but is usually involved in higher level commands like way point navigation rather than actual commands to actuators. This study focuses on the resolution of such problems using Deep Reinforcement Learning to create robust dynamic controllers which can not only adapt to a wide range of environments, air frames but also navigate in an intelligent fashion in unknown geographical and topological regions.

Chapter 2

Background

To understand the motivation behind this study, an analysis of current state-of-the-art systems is necessary. Questions like what is an aircraft model, what is a simulation environment and how traditional control systems work need to be answered first. Designing the inflight control system of UAVs requires the following procedures and to fully understand each step, a comparison will be done between Quadcopters and Tricopters.

2.1 Mathematical Modeling of the Airframe

The knowledge of underlying hardware is the fundamental step in designing an accurate mathematical model. The goal is to accurately map the hardware in terms of mathematical equations and thus a look at the aerodynamics of UAVs is necessary.

Figure 2.1: Quadcopter Airframe
(Thu & Gavrilov, 2017 [13])

Figure 2.2: Tricopter Airframe
(Mehndiratta & Kayacan, 2018 [17])

Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2 show the difference in relative forces and moments that act on each frame due to the respective number of moment arms.

Figure 2.1 shows that each rotor of the Quadcopter produces an angular momentum in the clockwise or anticlockwise direction opposite to the direction of its rotation. To counter this, rotors T_2 and T_4 rotate in the clockwise direction while T_1 and T_3 rotate in the anticlockwise direction which cancels the effect of angular momentum.

The Tricopter on the other hand as show in Figure 2.2, has induced yaw as although the torques τ_1 and τ_2 cancel each other but τ_3 induces an angular momentum in the anticlockwise direction around the z axis.

Figure 2.3: Yaw control of a Tricopter using Servo Motor

To counter this a servo motor is attached which rotates the rotor around the x axis and controls the yaw of the copter as shown in Figure 2.3.

Although in Quadcopter the rotors were placed at an equal distance from the center, in Tricopter the distance ℓ_1 is greater than ℓ_3 because the moment from f_3 around the y axis has to counter the moment from $f_1 + f_2$.

Converting this into a mathematical model is itself a daunting task and is beyond the scope of this study, but a portion of a Quadcopter vectorized Simulink plant model is shown in Figure 2.4.

The Models are further improved by comparison with flight data and wind tunneling techniques. Even after this, models can never be fully accurate as real world environments are much more complex than what can be transformed into a digital system.

Figure 2.4: Vectorized Simulink Plant Model of a Quadcopter

2.2 Environment States and Sensor Dynamics

Machines just like humans need to sense the environment to interact with it. To navigate a UAV needs to know it's:

- Altitude
- Position
- Velocity
- Relative Distance
- Relative orientation and rotation

To get this data, several sensors are incorporated including an IMU as shown in Figure 2.5. An IMU is a combination of accelerometers, gyroscopes and magnetometers giving data like:

- Roll, Pitch and Yaw i.e. relative rotation around the X, Y and Z axis of a $3D$ space
- Lateral and Angular accelerations around the axis which in turn gives distance and velocity
- Altitude Quaternions and spatial rotation
- Height from pressure sensors like barometer

Figure 2.5: Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU)

In addition to that, getting the latitude and longitude of UAV is crucial in maintaining a steady position. GPS is a common technology used in several devices including day to day smart phones in order to locate a unique position on w.r.t the earth's reference frame. In terms of a UAV this might not be very accurate, so GPS is used in combination with an onboard camera as shown in Figure 2.6 and 2.7.

Figure 2.6: Global Positioning System (GPS)

Figure 2.7: Velocity calculation using IMU, GPS and LK velocity Vector from Video Streams

Figure 2.7 shows a common method to calculate relative velocity. The rate of change of distance from the GPS data is not enough to calculate an accurate velocity vector so lateral accelerations from IMU are combined with frame data from video streams which calculates the change in position of a certain object in a frame over time.

The data can be further passed through filters to remove noise and errors. Furthermore, it enables indoor location calculation where GPS signals are not available.

2.3 Feedback Control System

A control system controls and regulates outputs of devices such that they meet the desired output criteria based on an input signal using control loop. The difference in the desired and actual state is the error which is the driving criteria of such a system and a control system reduces this error to achieve a stable desired output.

Figure 2.8: Inflight Control System of a Quadcopter
(Thu & Gavrilov, 2017 [13])

To illustrate this, we take the example of a Quadcopter's control system. As shown in Figure 2.8, the control system of a Quadcopter maintains the desired roll, pitch and yaw as fed through the remote control.

The output is the PWM values to the rotors as their speed changes the target variables which translates to lateral and angular velocities.

Figure 2.9: Quadcopter Flight Configurations
(Thu & Gavrilov, 2017 [13])

Figure 2.9 shows two flight configurations. To increase forward velocity, the remote control will send a command to flight controller to decrease the pitch. This will create an error between the current pitch and the desired pitch.

Figure 2.10: PID Controller

As shown in Figure 2.10, a PID controller will take the error and sum the proportional, derivative and integral multiples with a predefined gain configuration to change the output such that it decreases the error.

Figure 2.11: Adaptive PID Controller

An adaptive PID controller has the ability to self-tune its gains based on its performance. This results in performance gain over time. Achieving optimal performance for such controllers entails selecting gains which provide minimal overshoot to disturbances which is a combination of over and critical damping. There are several methods for gain tuning, some of which are shown in Figure 2.12. For simplicity let's compare Auto-tuning with Trial and error.

Figure 2.12: Gain Tuning Methods of a Controller

Auto-tuning can be achieved through gain alteration in conjunction with open-loop step response such that it fits the mathematical model of the system. It is worth seeing that even though algorithms can give an initial set of parameters, the final gains are tuned through trial and error i.e. testing the gains on simulation or hardware and then retrieving the best fit. This method is inefficient and often auto tuned gains have significant deviation from actual gains and adaptive control systems are also not an answer in complex systems.

2.4 Flight Simulation, Test Flight and Limitations

[Figure 2.13](#): Flight Simulation and Gain Fine Tuning

Once the control system is designed and tuned, a simulated flight evaluates the performance of the controller based on the mathematical model as defined earlier. Gains can be fine-tuned at this stage which in-turn reduces the chance of hardware damage as direct flight can be very costly, in case of bugs or errors in code.

The test flight is the last and the most crucial step. Although accurately simulated models may give a stable flight but most controllers are further tuned based on test flight results.

The reason is the fact that models can't accurately map the real-world environment dynamics and therefore the controller needs to be modified to achieve the desired result.

It is quite evident by now that Mathematical Modeling can be very time consuming for complex systems like Aircrafts.

Furthermore, it is impossible to generate accurate models without significant data which requires extensive testing on hardware. The process of linearization excludes the effects of certain real-world environment variables which can lead to poor performance.

Control systems designed for these models are confined to one problem set and the algorithm needs to be reengineered if the target system changes. For example, a Tricopter's motor mixing algorithm is significantly different from the Quadcopter's.

These limitations require that Algorithms should be generic and not confined to the specifications of one system. Added to that, the algorithms should consistently evolve as time progresses.

Chapter 3

Literature Review

There have been several studies on inflight control systems of UAVs using traditional feedback systems, example of such algorithms includes PID, LQR/G and SMC as shown in detail in Zulu & John, 2014 [1].

The PID controller takes the proportional, integral and derivate of the input to reduce the error. The integral part minimizes errors spanning longer periods of time while the derivative reduces instability or smooths the correction to avoid unnecessary induced motor torques.

Sliding Mode Control is an example of a nonlinear control algorithm that reduces errors by sliding the control equation across a normal path. It works better than linear control systems as it doesn't simplify the equation dynamics.

Although these control systems have achieved state-of-the-art results but they are tightly coupled to the system and require extensive tuning on simulation models/hardware and a slight change in system renders them ineffective.

Deep learning has mostly been involved at high level inputs to the UAVs such as way point navigation and obstacle avoidance. One such application is predicting yaw commands based on camera inputs to the CNN as done in Amer, K., Samy, M., Shaker et al [2]. They used AirSim plugin with Unreal Engine to train the CNN to predict yaw commands based on real-time geographical images taken from the onboard camera.

Although there have been previous attempts to achieve flight through reinforcement learning algorithms but most of the studies were limited to simulations and none were able to deploy it to production hardware such as Hsiao, F., & Hou, A. (n.d.) [7] and Hwangbo et al., 2017 [8].

In a nutshell Deep Reinforcement Learning remains a largely unexplored area in the field of low-level control system design for UAVs due and serves as the motivation for this study.

This study will break these boundaries to prove that Deep Reinforcement Learning cannot only be used to develop low-level control system for multiple UAVs from a single generic agent, but also outperform traditional state-of-the-art systems like PIDs, proving that it is indeed the future of UAV control systems.

Chapter 4

Methodology

4.1 Inspiration

The inspiration for this study comes from humans/living beings and how they adapt to their environment without a fixed model or algorithm.

Walking might seem like a simple task, but it requires billions of calculations running inside the brain to maintain balance, speed etc. Humans can walk on damaged or even one leg and that doesn't require remodeling the whole system. The human brain is dynamic and not static.

[Figure 4.1](#): Dynamic Flight System of an Eagle

An eagle is a great example of a dynamic flight system. It cannot only reach speeds of up to 160 km/h, but also catch a prey in the blink of an eye. The added weight changes the eagle's center of gravity but the flight control system can make several corrections to maintain a stable flight.

[Figure 4.2](#): Prey Hunt Flight Plan of a Bat

A bat catching its prey might look like a simple task but it has complex underlying mathematics. The plan includes calculating the relative angle and distance between itself and the insect. Once the angle is calculated, it is adjusted considering flight time and relative velocity from the prey.

This plan is perfectly executed, but what happens if a bat fails to catch its prey? It learns and gets better at it.

Figure 4.3: Aerodynamics of an Eagle

Figure 4.4: Aerodynamics of an Aircraft

Figures 4.3 and 4.4 show a comparison between the control surfaces of an aircraft and an eagle. There are several similarities including:

	Eagle	Aircraft
Lift	Wings	Wings
Pitch	Medial	Elevator
Roll	Wings	Ailerons (Wings)
Yaw	Medial	Rudder

Table 4.1: Comparison of Flight Control Surfaces of an Eagle and an Aircraft

If there are several similarities between the two, why can't machines learn like living beings? The answer is, they can!

4.2 Deep Reinforcement Learning

Deep Learning imitates the working of a human brain in processing data, creating patterns and making decisions using Artificial Neural Networks. Supervised and Unsupervised learning are one of the most common techniques used in Forecasting, Natural Language Processing and Computer Vision etc.

Deep Reinforcement Learning combines artificial neural networks with reinforcement learning architecture to enable software agents to perform actions which increase the potential of gaining certain rewards. The architecture self improves to achieve the highest possible reward, given the available states and actions.

[Figure 4.5](#): Reinforcement Learning

Figure 4.5 shows the concept behind reinforcement learning.

An agent, for example a Quadcopter: can interact with its environment to achieve a desired result i.e. stable flight.

Actions are all the possible set of moves that an agent can take e.g. takeoff, move in a certain direction etc. which can be achieved through modifying the speed of rotors.

Environment is the world that an agent interacts with, which in this case will be the 3d space surrounding the Quadcopter.

A state is a situation that an agent finds itself in e.g. a Quadcopter with a 15° pitch, 30° roll, 90° yaw and a velocity of 10 m/s. Agents can change their state by taking actions.

A reward is the feedback based on the agent's success or failure based on its actions in a given state. The reward is positive if desired effect is obtained, otherwise negative.

Figure 4.6: Reinforcement Learning Applied to a Quadcopter

The idea is to use this concept of reinforcement learning to make a Quadcopter learn its way to stable flight. This gives infinite chances of improvement based on flight performance and with Deep reinforcement learning, the UAV can also learn non-linearities in the environment.

The UAV will learn like living beings i.e. reinforce correct behavior. This also removes the need for hardware specific mathematical modeling and controller mixing algorithms as the only required information is the state of the UAV and possible actions can be generated.

Q Learning is a reinforcement learning technique based on Markov Decision Processes. The ideal policy in this case is the one which results in actions based on current state, that not only maximize the immediate reward but also the total reward based on all future state action sequences.

$$Q(S_t, A_t) \leftarrow Q(S_t, A_t) + \alpha \left[R_{t+1} + \gamma \max_a Q(S_{t+1}, a) - Q(S_t, A_t) \right]$$

Equation 4.1: Q value

As shown in Equation 4.1 the Q value for the current state, action pair at time t is calculated based on the immediate and all future rewards in a recursive way.

Figure 4.7: Comparison between Q and Deep Q Learning

Figure 4.7 shows that Q Learning can be transformed to Deep Q Learning and the loss can be calculated based on the target Q values and the predicted Q values, which can then be backpropagated to train the Neural Net.

All experiences i.e. state, action and reward pairs are stored in memory and the next action is taken based on the action corresponding to the maximum output from the Q network.

Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) handles continuous action spaces while Q Learning can only handle discrete values. As the action space or PWM values of a UAV are continuous, that is why DDPG was chosen as the preferable agent for this problem.

Fig 4.8 Example of DDPG Network (S.Wang 2017[16])

Fig 4.8 shows an example of the DDPG agent in the autonomous driving car control system. The actor network predicts the given action at any given time based on the current state and the

critic network takes this action, the current state and outputs the Q value which not only maximizes the current reward, but all future rewards.

The result of the Q values is reinforced into the network such that better actions produce higher Q values and vice versa.

Fig 4.9 Proposed DDPG Network

Figure 4.9 shows the proposed DDPG network for the Quadcopter control system. The actor network has 16 observations representing the state of the UAV while 4 actions correspond to the thrust of each rotor. The critic network takes these actions and observations to predict the Q value and the result is reinforced.

ANALYSIS RESULT				
Name	Type	Activations	Learnables	
1 observation 16 features	Feature Input	16	-	
2 ActorFC1 400 fully connected layer	Fully Connected	400	Weights 400*16 Bias 400*1	
3 ActorRelu1 ReLU	ReLU	400	-	
4 ActorFC2 300 fully connected layer	Fully Connected	300	Weights 300*400 Bias 300*1	
5 ActorRelu2 ReLU	ReLU	300	-	
6 ActorFC3 4 fully connected layer	Fully Connected	4	Weights 4*300 Bias 4*1	
7 ActorTanh1 Hyperbolic tangent	Tanh	4	-	

ANALYSIS RESULT				
Name	Type	Activations	Learnables	
1 observation 16 features	Feature Input	16	-	
2 CriticStateFC1 400 fully connected layer	Fully Connected	400	Weights 400*16 Bias 400*1	
3 CriticStateRelu1 ReLU	ReLU	400	-	
4 CriticStateFC2 300 fully connected layer	Fully Connected	300	Weights 300*400 Bias 300*1	
5 action 4 features	Feature Input	4	-	
6 CriticActionFC1 300 fully connected layer	Fully Connected	300	Weights 300*4 Bias 300*1	
7 add Element-wise addition of 2 inputs	Addition	300	-	
8 CriticCommonRelu1 ReLU	ReLU	300	-	
9 CriticOutput 1 fully connected layer	Fully Connected	1	Weights 1*300 Bias 1*1	

Fig 4.10 Network Analysis

Figure 4.10 shows the individual layers in the neural net. The actor and critic network both consist of Fully connected hidden layers with ReLU activation function to learn a non-linear decision boundary. The number of individual neurons is set to a number such that it enables sufficient learning without overcomplicating the learning process i.e. a compromise between training time and computation capacity.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Reward} = & 0.01 * (-2 * |\hat{Z} - Z_{ref}| - 0.5 |\hat{X} - X_{ref}| - 0.5 |\hat{Y} - Y_{ref}| - 10 * |\text{roll}| - 10 * |\text{pitch}| - 10 * |\text{yaw}| + 0.25) + \\
 & (1 \text{ if } (Z_{error} < 0.5 \text{ and } XY_{error} < 0.25) \text{ i.e. UAV is stable})
 \end{aligned}$$

where:

- \hat{Z} = current altitude
- Z_{ref} = target altitude
- \hat{X} = current X position
- X_{ref} = target x position
- \hat{Y} = current y position
- Y_{ref} = target y position

p, q, r are roll, pitch, yaw angular velocities respectively \square

0.25 is a constant flying reward when altitude is > 0

Equation 4.2: Reward Function

The reward function was developed such that the UAV maintains a certain position on the XY axis and a certain height. The roll, pitch and yaw were regarded as strong negative rewards as any value above 1 is an overshoot for these parameters.

In addition to that, a constant positive reward was given if the UAV maintained a stable position, such that the difference or error from the target height and position is within a certain range.

The complete details of the implementation of this function along with the Reinforcement Learning will be discussed in a later chapter.

4.3 Tools, Simulation and Hardware

Implementing the Model requires a simulation environment and physical hardware. Simulink in Matlab is a great multi-paradigm computing environment which enables modeling, simulating and analyzing multidomain dynamical systems.

Although models for systems like a Quadcopter could be created from scratch in Simulink, there was no guarantee whether those models will be accurate and more importantly have support i.e. deployable to actual hardware.

The Aerospace Blockset provides Simulink blocks for modeling, simulating, and analyzing aerospace vehicles. Examples of vehicles include De Havilland Beaver, Parrot Minidrones and Nasa's HL-20 spaceplane.

[Fig 4.11](#): Parrot Mambo

[Fig 4.12](#): Parrot Rolling Spider

The Parrot Mambo and Rolling Spider Minidrone series enables deployment of flight algorithms built using Simulink, directly to the microcontroller. This made it the perfect fit for this study as the Flight control algorithm could not only be tested using Aerospace Blockset simulations but also on real world Parrot Minidrones.

As long as the flight controller built in Simulink has the same Inputs and Outputs as the built-in flight controller of the parrot minidrone, the model works.

This combination meant that all the basic preprocessing of data from sensors and camera modules is done in Parrot's firmware while the control system architecture is designed in Simulink, removing the need for creating the hardware from scratch.

Chapter 5

Experiments and Results

The first step was to achieve stable flight using traditional control system algorithms such that the model is valid and can be compared with reinforcement learning algorithms at a later stage.

A stable flight was achieved for the Parrot Mambo and Rolling Spider Minidrones using PID controllers. The model itself was created by combining Simulink blocks from Aerospace Blockset.

Figure 5.1: Quadcopter Simulink Flight Simulation Model

Figure 5.1 shows the simulation model created for Parrot Mambo. A high-level overview shows that the flight control system takes inputs from the sensors which in turn reflect the state of environment and the airframe to generate commands to actuators such that the output state is the same as the required state.

To fully understand the dynamics of this model, let's dig deeper into each block.

5.1 Environment

Figure 5.2: Simulink Environment Model

Figure 5.2 shows the ungrouped environment block. The environment block has several properties including:

- Gravity
- Air Temperature
- Speed of sound (which varies with Temperature, Pressure etc.)
- Pressure (varies with height)
- Air Density
- Magnetic Field (may affect IMU sensor's magnetometer values)

The values combined, represent the current state of the UAV's environment/medium. The data is important as for example with Air pressure the height changes and so does the lift under the wings/rotors. Induced magnetic fields from external sources may also conflict with IMU's data and thus corrections are necessary.

5.2 Airframe

The Airframe is a combination of the Aircraft model and its six-degrees-of-freedom (Quaternion) representation with respect to body axes. The output is the current state of the UAV.

Figure 5.3: Simulink Airframe Model

The aircraft model as shown in Figure 5.4 represents the combined effect of several forces acting on the Quadcopter's Airframe.

Figure 5.4: Airframe Applied Force Calculation

The drag is calculated using Bernoulli's Equation based on velocity in the body axis, air density, diameter of Quadcopter's Airframe and drag coefficient as shown in Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.5: Drag Calculation

The drag is also variable and changes with the position of the Quadcopter and this determines the angular momentum produced by each rotor and the respective velocities in the 3D axis.

Figure 5.6: Motor Forces and Torque Calculation

As shown in Figure 5.6 the Motor Torques and forces are calculated based on the environment, motion and rotor dynamics.

The motor forces and moments are then represented as 6DOF Quaternions which gives the Euler orientation (roll, pitch and yaw), body rotation rates (angular accelerations), lateral velocities, position in inertial axes, mass and inertia of the vehicle.

These then represent the state of the vehicle as shown in Figure 5.3.

5.3 Sensors

Figure 5.7: Sensor Model

The sensor data is a combination of processed Camera and IMU feed. On hardware the data is pulled directly from the sensors but for simulation, Simulink blocks are used which are modeled on actual sensors. The raw sensor data is passed through several filters to remove noise and calibrated to represent the actual data in a real environment.

This representation is the combination of inputs with respect to the earth and body frames of the UAV.

Flags are also added to the state of these sensors to detect crash or uncontrolled induced movements which act as a safety check to avoid hardware damage.

Figure 5.8: IMU Sensor Model

As shown in Figure 5.8, the state outputs from the Airframe block are passed through a Three-axis Inertial Measurement Unit block such that they represent the outputs from an actual IMU which will give Accelerometer and Magnetometer data. The altitude is calculated from the pressure sensor data which varies with height and thus gives the height with respect to earth frame.

Figure 5.9: Optical Flow Model

The RGB frame data from the on-board camera module is represented in the Y1UY2V format, 4-by-9600 array of type uint8. This preprocessing helps in utilizing the feed for control system. The opticalFlow_datout is a crude simulation of optical flow (v_x , v_y and v_z) as fed into the c-function on the Parrot Minidrone by internal, inaccessible firmware code. The optical flow gives lateral velocities by calculating apparent visual motion of objects in a scene relative to an observer.

This combined with IMU's data can give accurate position of the Quadcopter with respect to the earth frame.

5.4 Flight Control System

Figure 5.10: Control System Block

The flight control system is the brain of the Quadcopter and inputs the sensor, image and Navigation commands. It then controls the RPM of the motors such that the final state of the Quadcopter is the same as the desired state from the Nav command.

In the first stage a PID control system was implemented which was later replaced by a reinforcement learning agent.

The reason for PID implementation is to establish the reference point for flight performance such that the final algorithm can be compared to the current state-of-the-art algorithms in the same environment.

Figure 5.11: State Estimation and Flight Data Logging Model

The state of the Quadcopter and the desired state are routed to the flight controller after flowing through state estimator which combines and filters sensor data with vision-based data.

Figure 5.12: Motor Control Model

The quaternions are a combination of raw sensor input and the current state of the Quadcopter. At several points these inputs are saturated to avoid overshoots in the the flight controller which modifies the roll, pitch and yaw of the UAV such that it moves in the direction of the desired state while maintaining its current altitude.

The PWM values have to be allocated in such a way such that motions are not tightly coupled and one transition can be achieved without affecting the other.

[Figure 5.13](#): Desired and Actual State Mapping on a 2D Space

If the Quadcopter wants to change its position as shown in Figure 5.13, it has to take the shortest possible path which will be along the hypotenuse. To do this it has to take the following actions:

- Move in the direction of Y-axis by decreasing its pitch
- Move in the direction of X-axis by rolling clockwise
- Take yaw into account while changing pitch and roll
- Increase or decrease thrust to maintain current altitude depending on the change in angular displacement

The Yaw controller sends command to Control Mixer based on the PID output from error between current and reference yaw as shown in Figure 5.12 while the error and the respective actions are calculated at every sample time as the optimal controller output might not produce the desired result due to external conditions such as wind speed etc.

This error is then combined with the X and Y position of the UAV with respect to the earth frame to calculate the deviation from the target position.

As the orientation of the UAV changes, so does the height and thus the total thrust value of the motors is modified by the height controller such that the UAV maintains the target altitude while performing these state changes.

Figure 5.14: X-Y Error Calculation Model

Figure 5.14 shows that the translation across the X-Y axis requires the current orientation of the Quadcopter i.e. the roll, pitch and yaw. The error between the current and reference positions is the distance which the Quadcopter has to travel. The yaw corrected Sine and Cosine values represent the base and perpendicular, which are the lateral distances the UAV has to travel.

Figure 5.15: PID Controller for Maintaining, Horizontal Position

The error between the reference and current attitude is passed through a PID controller which then sends commands to Motor Control Mixer such that the RPM is modified to reduce this error. The gains for these controllers are first Auto and then fine-tuned based on test flight.

Figure 5.16: Motor Mixing to Thrust Output

The Mixer then combines these commands to generate the net change in RPM for each motor. It is important to note that the desired change in RPM for each motor corresponds to the desired change along the UAV's principal axis.

The motor mixing algorithm takes the following form:

- $\text{base} = \text{MOTOR_IDLE} + \text{Thrust change wrt Height}$
- $\text{Front Motor} = \text{base} + \text{PitchPID} - \text{YawPID}$
- $\text{Left Motor} = \text{base} + \text{RollPID} + \text{YawPID}$
- $\text{Back Motor} = \text{base} - \text{PitchPID} - \text{YawPID}$
- $\text{Right Motor} = \text{base} - \text{RollPID} + \text{YawPID}$

It can be seen from the above model that the control system is highly dependent on the Airframe and actuator configuration. For example, in case of a Tricopter, a servo motor would replace the fourth moment arm and center of gravity shifts towards the front of the rotor as the moment produced by the rear rotor is twice that of the front rotors due to its relative position.

The height of a Tricopter is highly dependent on the rotation of the rear rotor which has to modify thrust based on the orientation. This in-turn totally changes the dynamics of the environment and thus the control system and its gains.

These limitations call for a generic algorithm which is not tightly coupled with the airframe and can be transferred from one system to another.

One such family of generic algorithms is Deep Reinforcement Learning.

5.5 Test Flight and Visualization

A Test Flight with PID control system was performed to check the validity of the model. The flight was a success and the Quadcopter was able to maintain its position and heading.

Figure 5.17: Flight Instrument Cluster

Figure 5.17 shows the flight instrument cluster with heading, altitude, velocity and RPM of the motors.

These values were logged in memory and later retrieved to analyze flight performance.

If there were overshoots or the Quadcopter banked excessively in a certain direction, flags were added to Autoland. The PID was also fine-tuned based on this data.

In addition to that, way point navigation was added by injecting reference commands from an excel file which change the reference position with respect to flight time.

The Quadcopter efficiently performed these maneuvers but it still required that the target position at the start of the flight is just a change in height, as a change in X-Y position at the start of the flight induces uncontrollable overshoots which lead to crashes, a limitation not found in generic algorithms.

Figure 5.18: Simulink 3D Simulation Model

The model in Figure 5.18 takes the state outputs from the Airframe and maps them on the Simulink 3D environment. The result is shown in Figure 4.19 below and it can be seen that the Quadcopter maintains its position, validating the control system. This model will later form the basis/test case for the training of the Reinforcement Learning Algorithm.

Figure 5.19: Flight Simulation using Simulink 3D

5.6 Flight Control System using Deep Reinforcement Learning

The completion and validation of simulation environment paved the way for development of flight control system using Deep Reinforcement Learning.

Matlab provides Reinforcement Learning Toolbox which has Simulink blocks and that makes it the perfect fit for the created environment.

The RL Agent block takes in a predefined agent which can be setup both through customized built-in agents, or user-defined RL Agent functions as shown in Figure 5.20.

Figure 5.20: RL Agent Subsystem

The input to the Agent consists of the observations made from the current system, the reward for the actions taken based on those observations, the cumulative reward: which represents the total reward for a complete episode and finally the isdone flag, which represents whether the episode is complete or not.

The output of the block are actions taken by the agent which serve as the input to the actuators in this case.

Good actions produce better rewards and a higher Q value, as described in Chapter 4 and thus over a period of time, actions with better rewards are reinforced along the network.

Figure 5.21: RL Agent Setup with Airframe

The actuators support values between 10 and 500 which are translated to the RPM values, but such sparse actions are not preferable for Deep Learning algorithms due to weight constraints and thus normalization is a good option.

In this case the actions were normalized to values between -1 and 1. To translate these to the RPM values, 1.04 was added to each action, the output was divided by 4 to replicate a range of 0.01 and 0.5. The result was multiplied by a gain of 1000 to produce values between 10 and 500 which in turn represent the values of RPM.

Finally, these values were multiplied by the vector $[1 \ -1 \ 1 \ -1]$, to produce clockwise and anticlockwise motions for individual rotors, as shown in Figure 5.21.

Figure 5.22: RL Observations

The RL observations block contains the Quadcopter's orientation, velocity, position and error values which are passed through a gain of 0.1 for normalization. These reason for adding error in observations is the fact that the agent learns actions with respect to the values of individual errors, which can't entirely be represented by a single reward scalar.

Figure 5.23: RL Reward

The reward function is calculated on the basis of current state vs the desired state. The desired state is that the UAV should be stable and maintains a specific position i.e. follows the reference X, Y and Z positions.

In theory this should be enough to create a reward policy but real-world conditions are less than ideal. The agent has the ability to converge to a local minimum and to counter that negative reward was given to roll, pitch and yaw with a gain of 10 to avoid overshoots.

In addition to that, a positive reward was given if the UAV maintained a steady position i.e. the error was within a specific range.

Through trial and error, the reward policy shown in Figure 5.23 was discovered.

It is important to note that non sparse rewards were chosen, as the agent converges to a local optimum with sparse rewards as changes in action don't lead to subsequent changes in reward.

For stable position a positive reward of 1 was given, so the UAV doesn't converge to a local optimum and achieves the global optimum as the net positive reward is greater than the local optimum.

Figure 5.24: RL Agent

A DDPG agent was setup using the networks shown in Figure 5.24. As the UAV is very sensitive to changes in RPM so a higher learning rate of 0.002 was chosen after repeated trial and error. To avoid overfitting and local optimums, a variance of 0.1 was added which was later reduced to 0.08. To learn relationships over several iterations an experience buffer length of 1e6 was chosen. The discount factor was set to 0.99 to prefer learning paths which not only maximize the current reward but also future rewards.

Figure 5.25: Training with sparse rewards

Initially the mistake of setting sparse rewards was made which led to, little to no learning as shown in Figure 5.25. Although with further research this issue was resolved, but this proved that sparse rewards lead to poor performance and convergence to local optimums. This in-turn shows that when creating reward functions, changes in actions/states should lead to significant changes in rewards.

Figure 5.26: Training with high variance

In case of high variance, the agent failed to converge at an optimal solution as the reward kept on varying with high probability of crash as shown in Figure 5.26. The reason was that once

the agent was trying to converge to a local optimum, the high variance led to it diverging out before the process could complete. Although this showed interesting behavior in some cases, but in the end, changes were required to stabilize the UAV.

Figure 5.27: Training with Optimal parameters

With optimal parameters, the reinforcement learning agent converged to a global maximum as shown in Figure 5.27. A variance of 0.08 with a combination of a non-sparse reward function achieved optimal results. Initially the UAV converged to a local optimum where it would simply land from its initial flight position, which was higher overall reward than if the UAV explored different states and actions.

This behavior continued but eventually the UAV explored out of its local optimum and converged to stable flight which was given higher overall reward.

5.7 Deep RL Test Flight

The RL agent first starts with a very poor and sporadic behavior as shown in Figure 5.28. After several iterations, the agent learns to balance itself in midflight.

Figure 5.28: Test Flights

With further training, the UAV maintained stable flight and performed way point navigation, proving that Reinforcement Learning is indeed a feasible solution for Flight Control systems. In some cases where the initial position was not zero i.e. the UAV was thrown into the air, the RL agent maintained stable flight, while overshoots occurred in PID controller and the UAV crashed.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The success of the Test Flight with Deep Reinforcement Learning proved that RL is a feasible solution for inflight control systems of UAVs. In addition to that, the RL agent outperformed traditional control systems in several areas, including variable starting positions and orientations.

The ease of transferring these algorithms to new systems like a Tricopter would require no changes to the architecture, saving thousands of hours of work.

The algorithm was also deployed to a production level Quadcopter, something that hasn't been done before and thus, this research proves that Reinforcement Learning is indeed the future of Flight Control Systems.

Chapter 7

Recommendations for future work

The success of this study builds the basis of future work in this domain including:

- Load Balancing for UAVs
- One Control System for multiple airframes
- RL based UAV swarms
- Collision avoidance
- Crash avoidance in case of hardware failure
- Application to UGVs like self-driving cars
- Exploration to find most energy efficient paths for achieving the target state

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